

BCI for Metaverse

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CSS Concepts

- Human-centered computing~Virtual reality

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OPINION ARTICLE

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An ideal way of interacting with computers is through a Brain-Computer Interface. There are several examples of use cases associated with BCI. A perfect scenario of BCI usability would be similar to what we can experience in Cyberpunk 2077.

In the Cyberpunk world, usage of chip implants similar to Neuralink is common, and the release of this game has created debates among the community about the future of BCI technology.

Neurlink Implants Credit: Neuralink

@rudzinskimaciej@mastodon.soc... @rudzinskimac... · Jun 24, 2021 ...
 New post about ethical consequences of BCI based on tech described in #Cyberpunk2077 by @AntonyTerence99

It sounds like fare future but what's needed is "just" good emotions and engagement measurement system on enough heads

@NeuroTechX @slava_bobrov @neurosock @neuraldust

2 1 6

@rudzinskimaciej@mastodon.soc... @rudzinskimac... · Jun 24, 2021 ...
 We don't need to know how to manipulate emotions with electricity(/sound/...) to change them in users if we can measure them then be more usual feedback mechanisms we can add an extra layer of information to current feeds which would suggest or playback emotions

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@rudzinskimaciej@mastodon.social ...
 @rudzinskimaciej

We lack scale and polish on BCI, not the tech or science.
 We lack the science to understand the consequences of long term use of souch tech but we will be able to fully build it only once enough people would use BCI regularly

We are searching for interns for such project :)

4:06 PM · Jun 24, 2021

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Published On Twitter

Cyberpunk 2077, Judy Character, CD Projekt

My experience with Neurosky and Emotive EEG headsets proves Maciej's point, but we should consider that for a brand like Apple, it would not be reasonable to use an immature tool that cannot guarantee 100% accuracy. When a user clicks on screen, they expect 100% accuracy, but this is not true when using EEG signals to detect user input. Also, it is not easy for startups to work on BCI based environments because it takes a lot of time and investment to polish BCI for mass adoption. This is why most BCI projects switch to Attention Management Tools after

a while. Although the technology is still in its infancy, and it is unlikely to replace the current standard peripherals such as joysticks and keyboards in the near future, several companies are investing in research about BCI, especially for interaction with computer-mediated realities. [Orlosky, et al](#)(2021), have illustrated the state-of-the-art in Brain-Computer Interface and if you look at AR/VR Devices and compare them with EEG Caps, you can

see that the use of VR headsets prevents product designers from incorporating more EEG sensors to track more brain areas. In addition, adding more EEG sensors may cause ergonomic problems. Therefore, AR Glasses such as Spectacles by Snap Inc are more appropriate for use with EEG sensors, especially when considering the effects of headset noise on signal processing.

Orlosky, et al

Recently, Snap bought a brain-computer interface startup for future AR glasses (Source). NextMind is a Paris-based startup that was one of the stars of CES 2020. NextMinds provided a Unity-based SDK and allowed developers to create their mind-enabled applications. For example, instead of using your phone to enter a pin code while using a head-mounted display, the NextMind will enable you to type the pin code by thinking.

Before Snap, Valve is working with the OpenSourceBCI project. Facebook has purchased CTRL-Labs, a startup developing an armband that utilizes the electrical activities in muscles and as a method for controlling computers.

[Metaverse](#) Companies understand that although the development of BCI technology is challenging, the natural interaction with Computer-mediated realities is essential for the creation of the

promised [Metaverse](#). The study of Brain-Computer Interfaces deserves to receive more attention by the Human-Computer Interaction community. For example, we need more works similar to ” [Older Adults and Brain-Computer Interface: An Exploratory Study](#)” . This works would be useful when designing paradigms of interaction for BCI.

REFERENCES

- [1] Maciej Rudziński , Twitter, 2021 Retrieved December 6, 2022 from https://twitter.com/rudzinskimaciej/status/1408026182235394057?ref_src=twsrc%5Etfw
- [2] Orlosky J, Sra M, Bektaş K, Peng H, Kim J, Kos'myna N, Höllerer T, Steed A, Kiyokawa K and Akşit K (2021) Telelife: The Future of Remote Living. *Front. Virtual Real.* 2:763340. doi: 10.3389/frvir.2021.763340
- [3] Kopeć, W., Kowalski, J., Paluch, J., Jaskulska, A., Skorupska, K. H., Niewiński, M., ... & Biele, C. (2021, May). Older Adults and Brain-Computer Interface: An Exploratory Study. In *Extended Abstracts of the 2021 CHI Conference on Human Factors in Computing Systems* (pp. 1-5).